

Pearl Bipin <pearlbipin@gmail.com>

Re: [JIMS] Editor Decision. Response to Your Assessment.

1 message

Pearl Bipin <pearlbipin@gmail.com>

27 January 2026 at 23:04

To: "Dr. Pankaj Jain" <pankajkrjain@hotmail.com>

This "class note" was cited by an independent, unaffiliated third party in a reputed peer-reviewed journal, despite being a preprint. It has been cited in SAGE Journals, an outlet that is objectively far more prestigious and selective than JIMS.

Please do not underestimate work simply because it appears simple. As Richard Feynman famously said, "Any idiot can make the simple complex; it takes a genius to make the complex simple."

Your assessment tells me everything I need to know about the quality, standards, and intellectual depth of JIMS. I can state this clearly now: I will not be publishing any of my work in your journal. My work demonstrably deserves better avenues—and it has already received external, third-party validation from such avenues.

Additionally, please note the typo in your email: "lot cannot be considered as a research paper."
Attention to detail matters. Errors like this do not inspire confidence in your standards, nor do they strengthen baseless skepticism.

If you are curious about who you are dismissing, I suggest you Google "Pearl Bipin Pulickal." That alone should provide sufficient context.

Thank you for wasting my time.

You did not reject a weak submission, you lost a valuable asset.

Goodbye.

On Tue, Jan 27, 2026, 21:31 Dr. Pankaj Jain via Informatics Journals <editor@informaticsjournals.co.in> wrote:

Dear Pearl Bipin Pulickal:

The document is no more than class notes. It cannot be considered as a research paper. We therefore have reached a decision regarding your submission to The Journal of the Indian Mathematical Society, "An Elegant Expression for π in Terms of Complex Logarithms".

Our decision is to: Decline Submission

The Journal of the Indian Mathematical Society <https://informaticsjournals.co.in/index.php/jims>